

EFFECT OF GRADED LEVELS OF LYSINE ON LATE BEHAVIOR OF LAYING HENS IN NORTHERN GUINEA SAVANNA.

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ABSTRACT

An experiment was conducted with 120 beak trimmed 46 weeks old layers (Shika Brown Strain) to investigate the effect of varying lysine levels on late behaviour of the hens in deep litter system. Laying Hens were randomly allocated to 5 experimental diets containing varying lysine levels (0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 and 0.4%) each replicated 3 times. Behavioural observations were obtained using focal continuous sampling and instantaneous scan sampling methods, timed for 15 minute before feeding the hens and after feeding, respectively. The result indicated that both normal and stereotype behaviours increased significantly with increasing lysine level in the diet ($58.01 \pm 2.91\%$; $p < 0.01$) and ($18.60 \pm 1.32\%$; $p < 0.001$) respectively. It was therefore concluded that including 0.4% level of lysine in the diet of laying hens during the late laying period may affect the behaviour of the hens either positively or negatively during the dry season period in northern guinea savannah. Farmers in Nigeria could therefore control undesirable behaviours such as egg destruction and feather pecking through nutritional and other management factors for optimum flock performance.

KEYWORDS: laying hens; behavior; lysine; northern guinea savanna.

INTRODUCTION

The population of domestic chickens is higher than any other kind of poultry such as Duck, Turkey, Geese, Guinea fowl, Pigeons etc (Kekocha, 1984). Poultry plays an important role in employment and income generation as well as the supply of protein in human nutrition today. It is also vital in the supply of food and cash income especially in rural areas (Sonaiya, 1990). The most common housing systems for poultry comprised of the deep litter, free range or aviaries and more recently, furnished cages (Tauson, 2005). Furnished cages will be the only legal form of cage in the EU from 2012. Today, about 40% of layers in Sweden are kept in furnished cages (Tauson, 2005). Furnished cages have the advantage of reducing the stress of keeping layers on the floor and in conventional cages. The natural behavior of layers is exhibited and their physical condition is better in furnished than in conventional cages (Appleby *et al.*, 2002). However, in an attempt to improve the animal welfare, other problems such as feather pecking and cannibalism have been reported (Abrahamson and Tauson 1997; Shimmura *et al.*, 2006; Blokhuis *et al.*, 2007). Many studies have been carried out regarding group size in conventional battery cages, and reported that an increase in group size leads to higher mortality rates or a risk of cannibalism or feather pecking (Huber and Sebo, 2001). Despite enormous increase in poultry industry in Nigeria today, there is inadequate information about the effect of different inclusion levels of lysine on late behaviour of laying hens raised in deep litter system. This type of study will therefore help to improve laying hens' performance and reduce losses due to cannibalism, feather pecking, breaking of eggs and low egg productivity particularly during the dry season of the year. Hence, the objective of this study was to investigate the effect of graded levels of lysine on late behaviour of laying hens.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted in the Livestock unit of the Department of Animal Science, Faculty of Agriculture, Ahmadu Bello University, Samaru ($11^{\circ} 11' N$, $7^{\circ} 37' E$ and 675m above sea level), Northern Nigeria. A total of 120 beak trimmed 46 weeks old layers (Shika Brown Strain) were used for the experiment. The dimension of each pen was 2.37m by 1.64m with a total area of 3.89m² per pen. The height of the experimental house was 2.22m. Each pen contained perches (nest boxes), feeding troughs and drinkers. Saw dust was used as litter. Hens were housed with eight birds per pen. From 20 to 52 weeks of age, hens received the experimental diets. Hens were fed the experimental diets *ad libitum*. All birds had free access to water. Room temperature was about 25°C and health status of the hens was monitored daily. At 20 weeks of age, hens were allotted to 1 of 5 dietary treatments (lysine levels) according to a completely randomized design experimental procedure, with 5 replicates per treatment (Table 1). The levels of lysine included in the diet were 0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 and 0.4% respectively. Feeding of the birds was done in the morning about 8am each day. Feeds were supplied from a pre-weighed quantity and weekly feed consumption was measured accordingly. The total

eggs laid in each pen were collected and counted daily. Feeding troughs were raised up to the shoulder of the birds to avoid wastage of feed. In week 46, manual behavioural observations were made from which time budget of the hens per pen could be calculated. Behavioural observations were made from 8.30am until 11.00am. All pens were observed for 15 minutes before feeding the hens and after they have been fed respectively. All data recorded were obtained using focal continuous sampling and instantaneous scan sampling at 15 minutes interval. The behavior recording lasted for 7 weeks. The ethogram used for the study is presented in Table 2.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

All data generated from the study were analyzed using SPSS (2003, version 12.0). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to detect differences between the means. Significantly different means were separated using LSD (least significant differences) and Dunnett's Test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3 shows the effect of graded levels of lysine on behaviour of laying hens at 52 weeks of age. The results indicated that as the level of lysine in the diet increases, percentages of normal and stereotype behaviors increased significantly (58.01 ± 2.91 ; $p < 0.01$ and 18.60 ± 1.32 ; $p < 0.001$) respectively. The significant increase in normal and stereotype behaviours with increasing levels of lysine may be related to the external stimulus generated due to the presence of feed in the pens since nutrition has been reported to be one of the factors that can affect behaviour in laying hens (Blokhuis, 1989; van Krimpen *et al.*, 2005). Also, the significant high percentage of normal behaviour could be related to an increase in the quantity of feed consumed by individual hens as a result of frustration due to stereotype behaviours exhibited by few hens in the pens (Lindberg and Nicol, 1994). Our result is in agreement with the findings of Peguri and Coon, (1993) who reported that stereotype behaviour such as feather pecking in laying hens could lead to increased feed intake. From the results, percentage of other behaviours significantly decreased to (15.03 ± 4.61 ; $p < 0.001$) at higher levels of lysine inclusion. This indicated that the hens spent less time in activities such as dust bathing due to increasing interest in redirected behaviours of pecking resulting from life experiences and rearing conditions (Chow and Hogan, 2005). Previous studies have reported a relationship between ground pecking behaviour and dust bathing in matured laying hens (Vestergaard and Lisborg, 1993).

CONCLUSION

Nutritional deficiencies can affect performance of laying hens in different ways (van Krimpen *et al.*, 2005). Until now, the effect of graded lysine levels on late behaviour of laying hens during the dry season period remained unclear. This study shows that increasing lysine levels in the diet of laying hens during the late laying period may affect the behaviour of the hens either positively or negatively in dry season period in northern guinea savannah. Farmers could therefore control undesirable behaviours such as egg destruction and feather pecking through nutritional and other management factors for optimum flock performance. Further research to investigate the effect of graded levels of lysine on early behaviour in laying hens is needed to better have an insight about overall welfare of laying hens for high economic returns to poultry farmers in Nigeria.

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Table 1: Composition and calculated chemical content of the Experimental diets (%).

INGREDIENTS	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅
Maize	50	50	50	50	50
GNC	24	24	24	24	24
Maize Offal	15	14.9	14.8	14.7	14.6
Bone Meal	3.3	3.3	3.3	3.3	3.3
Limestone	7	7	7	7	7
Salt	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
lysine	-	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4
Methionine	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Layer Premix ¹	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Total (%)	100	100	100	100	100
Calculated Analysis					
M.E (Kcal/Kg DM)	2660	2660	2660	2660	2660
CP%	17	17	17	17	17
CF%	3.9	3.9	3.9	3.9	3.9
EE%	3.65	3.65	3.65	3.65	3.65
Ca%	3.64	3.61	3.58	3.54	3.51
P%	0.90	0.89	0.87	0.86	0.84
Lysine%	0.60	0.70	0.80	0.90	1.00
Methionine %	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.35

¹ Provided the following nutrients per kg of premix: vitamin A, 2,400,000 IU; vitamin D3, 480,000 IU; vitamin E, 8,000 mg; vitamin B1, 960 mg; vitamin B2, 2,400 mg; d-pantothenic acid, 3,200 mg; niacinamide, 9,600 mg; vitamin B6, 1,120mg; folic acid, 360 mg; vitamin B12, 5,000 µg; vitamin C, 20,000 mg; biotin, 20 mg; vitamin K3, 960 mg; choline chloride 60,000 mg; 20,000 mg; copper, 1,600 mg (as CuSO₄.5H₂O), iron, 13,000 mg (as FeSO₄.7H₂O); manganese 13,000 mg(as MnO₂); zinc, 10,000 mg (as ZnSO₄); cobalt, 80 mg (as CoSO₄.7H₂O); iodine, 200 mg (KI); selenium, 80 mg (as Na₂SeO₃.5H₂O)

Table 2: Ethogram of behaviours observed in laying hens at 46-52 weeks of age.

Behavior	Description
Stereotype	- Feather pecking, cannibalism, breaking of egg and fighting.
Play	- Playing with one another e.g. by the use of their beaks.
Normal	- Feeding, drinking, scratching, standing, and walking.
Vocalization	- Vocalizing.
Others	- Dust bathing, lying down, sleeping, resting etc.

Table 3: Behavior of laying hens at 52 weeks of age as affected by different inclusion levels of lysine in the diet.

Behaviour	T ₁ 0%lysine	T ₂ 0.1%lysine	T ₃ 0.2%lysine	T ₄ 0.3%lysine	T ₅ 0.4%lysine	SEM	LOS
Normal	22.50 ^c	31.11 ^b	38.34 ^b	38.27 ^b	58.01 ^a	2.91	**
Other	38.54 ^a	39.79 ^a	38.66 ^a	33.91 ^a	15.03 ^b	4.61	***
Play	5.43 ^a	6.46 ^a	5.16 ^a	2.15 ^b	1.15 ^c	0.63	***
Stereotype	4.15 ^c	4.74 ^c	14.75 ^a	8.75 ^b	18.60 ^a	1.32	***
vocalization	8.84 ^a	5.44 ^{ab}	2.92 ^b	8.56 ^a	3.35 ^b	0.84	*

Means with different superscripts along the column differ significantly (LSD).

LOS = Level of Significance, * = significant at < 0.05, ** = significant at < 0.01, *** = significant at < 0.001

SEM= Standard error of mean.